

Solving for the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Using Scaling

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It seems that there are a number of ways to solve for the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. In previous notes, we have argued that there are two independent approaches, one global and one local, both based on physical scenarios. The global approach involves maximizing \ln of a physical number of arrangements: $N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!$, where $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$, subject to the constraint: $\text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. Only if one uses Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ does one obtain $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$, i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution. In (1), it is suggested that this same approach is equivalent to the first law of thermodynamics. We consider this approach briefly here.

The second approach which we have discussed in previous notes is a local one restricted to $e_i + e_j = E_1 = \text{constant}$. In such a case, one has a uniform distribution for product $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ as long as $e_i + e_j = E_1$. This means any E_1 value is possible, even a value greater than E_{total} . This leads to $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ which yields $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ and is based on physical elastic scattering. An approximation, however, is built in here because there is no cutoff on e_i , i.e. $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j)$ allows for $e_i = .8E_{total}$, $e_j = .7E_{total}$ and $e_i + e_j = 1.5 E_{total}$ which is unphysical.

Here we discuss a third approach called scaling, which when coupled with an approximation that all e_i 's are possible (just as in the subset-uniform distribution approach), yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Through scaling, it is possible to show that $E_{ave} = T \text{ Number}$ so that $E_{ave}(T+dT) = (T+dT) \text{ Number}$. Number , however, contains integrals which involve T and so one may calculate the coefficient of the dT contribution to Number and it must be 0. One may then seek a solution for $p(e_i)$ which makes it zero and this turns out to be the Maxwell-Boltzmann result. We argue that one may anticipate this based on the local subset-uniform distribution approach.

Global and Local Approaches

We have discussed global and local physical approaches to finding the MB distribution in previous notes and so we briefly summarize here. In the global approach one maximizes the \ln of the number of physical arrangements:

$$N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i) ! \quad \text{where } n(e_i) = Np(e_i) \quad \text{subject to the constraint } \text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \quad ((1))$$

This is an exact approach and it is not until one makes the approximation (Stirling's):

$$\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) \quad ((2))$$

that one obtains $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$, ((3)) i.e. the MB distribution.

An alternative physical approach is the consideration of 2-body elastic scattering. This approach has an approximation automatically built-in. One considers a subset $e_i + e_j = E_1 = \text{constant}$ such

that one has a uniform distribution for $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ as long as $e_i+e_j=E_1$. E_1 , however, may take on any value, even ones greater than E_{total} , making this an approximation. Then:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ as long as } e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l \quad ((4))$$

This leads to $p(e_i) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$. From this local approach one may actually create a math function $F(p(e_i))$ such that

$$dF/dp(e_i) - 1/T e_i = 0 \quad ((5))$$

In particular, one may create Shannon's entropy: $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. We have pointed out, however, that this same result follows from the physical maximization of arrangements using Stirling's approximation.

First Law of Thermodynamics

In (1), it is argued that the MB distribution may be found using the first law of thermodynamics with $dV_{Volume} = 0$, i.e.

$$dE = TdS \quad ((6))$$

In (1), a full mathematical proof is given, but here we note the following. The maximization of the number of arrangements is performed by altering the functional form of the $p(e_i)$'s such that $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ holds. Now,

$$p(e_i) = p(e_i/T) \text{ where } T \text{ is a parameter which makes } e_i/T \text{ dimensionless and represents an } E_{(total)} \text{ value} \quad ((7))$$

Formally, when one maximizes using Lagrange multipliers, one can make any change to the function $p(e_i/T)$. This means that

$$p(e_i) + dT dp(e_i/T) / dT \quad ((8a))$$

is a possible change. As a result, one changes from an e_i at T to an e_i at $T+dT$. Nevertheless, the math procedure for such a change is the same as the math procedure for maximizing Shannon's entropy plus a Lagrange multiplier multiplied by $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. One simply has an extra dT factor which disappears because the RHS is 0. Thus, ((6)) which involves a dE change due to $T \rightarrow T + dT$, is consistent with dS also changing due to $T \rightarrow T+dT$ and this procedure is equivalent mathematically to the maximization of Shannon's entropy plus a Lagrange multiplier $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$.

Specifically, the T factor in front of dS in (96) remains constant, and one has:

$$e dp = - T (\ln(p) + 1) dp \quad ((8b))$$

((8b)) is identical to the maximization subject to constraint approach.

Scaling Approach

We now introduce another approach due to scaling. Like the global and local approaches described in the first section, it is also based on an approximation, namely that any e_i is allowable.

$$E_{\text{total}} = T \left\{ \int \frac{e}{T} p(e/T) \text{ constant } \sqrt{e} \, de \right\} / \left\{ \int \frac{e}{T} p(e/T) \text{ constant } \sqrt{e} \, de \right\} \quad ((9))$$

((9)) holds in three dimensions. Furthermore, one may consider $p(e)$ unnormalized in ((9)) because the normalization factor $C(T)$ divides out in the numerator and denominator.

The approximation we propose is to allow e to tend from 0 to infinite in the integral. This is the same approximation used in the local subset approach described in the first section. Thus:

$$E_{\text{total}} = T * \text{Number} \quad ((10))$$

((10)) means that if $T \rightarrow T+dT$ then

$$E_{\text{total}}(T+dT) = (T+dT) * \text{Number} \quad ((11))$$

In other words, the number in ((10)) does not change. This number, however, is based on integrals containing T and one may replace this by $T+dT$. Then, the coefficient of dT should be 0. Specifically, the integral is given in ((9)) and one has:

$$E_{\text{total}} = (T+dT) * \text{Number} =$$

$$\left\{ N_1 + \int \sqrt{e} \, de \frac{e}{T} \left(-\frac{dT}{T} \right) p(e) + \frac{e}{T} dT \frac{dp}{dT} \right\} / \left(N_2 + \int \sqrt{e} \, de \frac{dT}{T} \frac{dp}{dT} \right)$$

$$\text{Here Number} = N_1/N_2 \quad ((12))$$

We factor N_2 out of the denominator term and use $1/(1+d) = 1-d$ where $d \ll 1$.

If one considers the three terms proportional to dT , one has:

$$-N_1/N_2 \int \sqrt{e} \, de \frac{dp}{dT} \quad (\text{first term})$$

$$-dT/T \frac{1}{C(T)} E \quad (\text{second term})$$

$$\int \frac{e}{T} \frac{dp}{dT} \sqrt{e} \, de \quad (\text{third term}) \quad ((13))$$

At this point, one has no idea what $p(e)$ is as the goal is to find such a function such that:

first term + second term + third term = 0 ((14))

Although there are ways to solve such an integral-differential equation, we propose using a trial $p(e)$ which drops with e very rapidly (due to the approximation made at the beginning of this section) and satisfies ((14)). We suggest (and give arguments for this in the next section) that

$$p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e/T) \quad ((15))$$

This result may then be checked with experiment. We do not need to worry about normalization because $C(T)$ cancels from the numerator and denominator in ((9)).

To see that ((15)) is the case, we first calculate 'Number' in ((10)) and find:

Number = $3/2$ ((16)) for three dimensions for:

$E = \text{Number} * T$ using the integrals in ((9)) if $p(e) = \exp(-e/T)$.

((16)) is well-known for an ideal gas. Next, we calculate the terms in ((13)).

First term $-3/2 \frac{1}{TT} \frac{1}{C(T)} E$

Second term $- \frac{1}{TT} \frac{1}{C(T)} E$

The third term may be obtained using integration by parts and yields:

$$+ \frac{1}{TT} \frac{1}{C(T)} E \quad (2.5) \quad ((14))$$

Note: one originally has the integral $\int_0^{\infty} y^{2.5} dy \exp(-y)$ where $y=e/T$ which explains the presence of 2.5 (coming from integration by parts). As a result, ((14)) is satisfied by $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e/T)$.

Relation with the Local Subset Method

We note that the approximation made in the scaling approach of the last section, namely that e ranges from 0 to infinite is exactly the same approximation made in the local subset, $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ uniform distribution approach which uses $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$. This latter approach yields $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ and so one might expect an identical solution for the scaling method, which is why we simply introduced $p(e) = C(T)\exp(-e/T)$ as a trial solution in the above section.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we present a scaling approach in this note, but suggest that there are at least three other methods which may be used to find the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e/T)$. We have discussed a global maximization of the \ln of physical arrangements $N!$

Product over i $n(e_i)!$ Subject to Sum over i $e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ in previous notes. If one uses Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$, one obtains the MB distribution. We show that this arrangement approach is identical to using the first law of thermodynamics proposed in (1) because a change in the function $p(e_i/T)$ is not restricted to one which enforces Sum over i $e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ if one uses Lagrange multipliers.

An independent approach is assume elastic 2-body scattering with no limit on the value of e , i.e. $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$, which also yields the MB distribution.

Finally, we propose a third method which is not based on a physical scenario, namely scaling with e allowed to range from 0 to infinite. Thus, one sees that all of the methods require approximations in order for $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ to emerge. The approximation used in the scaling approach is the same as that for the local subset approach. The scaling approach leads to an integral -differential equation and given the approximation, one may try $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ as a possible solution. We show that it is in fact a solution and one which drops very quickly with rising e , which is required if all e values are allowed.

References

1. Plastino, A. and Curado, E. Generating Statistical Distributions Without Maximizing Entropy (2005)
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